

Appendix E – Protocol for extensive literature search (ELS), relevance screening and article evaluation to establish microbiological cut-off values for antimicrobials

The following protocol for extensive literature search (ELS) will be used in the context of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) Scientific Committee Guidance on the characterisation of microorganisms in support of the risk assessment of products used in the food chain (EFSA-Q-2024-00438).

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E.1. Description of the process

An ELS of studies related to the phenotypic analysis for antimicrobial resistance/susceptibility for microorganisms typically used in the food chain will be performed.

The process will be performed according to the following main steps:

- ELS for potentially relevant citations;
- relevance screening to select the citations identified by the literature search, based on titles and abstract and then full text;
- evaluation of articles according to pre-specified criteria of phenotypic analysis for antimicrobial resistance/susceptibility;
- discussion between experts to come to a collective expert evaluation of the outcome, reflected in the EFSA Guidance on the characterisation and risk assessment of microorganisms used in the food chain.

Considering the purpose of the cut-off values, a broad search will be performed.

The review questions will be broken down into key elements using the PECO conceptual model:

- Population of interest (P)
- Exposure of interest (E)
- Comparator (C)
- Outcomes of interest (O).

E.1.1. Objective

The aim is to identify any publicly available studies reporting on phenotypic analysis for antimicrobial resistance/susceptibility for microorganisms typically used in the food chain (see Appendix C and D, tables).

For bacteria, ELS is focused on studies involving food-related strains, while for fungi, where horizontal gene transfer of resistance is uncommon, clinical isolates are prioritised.

E.1.2. Target population

The populations are bacteria and fungi typically used in the food chain.

a) Bacteria:

Bifidobacterium adolescentis, *Bifidobacterium animalis*, *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium breve*, *Bifidobacterium thermophilum*, *Bifidobacterium pseudolongum*, *Bifidobacterium pseudocatenulatum*, *Bifidobacterium catenulatum*, *Brevibacterium lactofermentum*, *Corynebacterium glutamicum*, *Corynebacterium jeikeium*, *Corynebacterium pseudodiphtheriticum*, *Corynebacterium minutissimum*, *Corynebacterium striatum*, *Corynebacterium urealyticum*, *Corynebacterium xerosis*, *Corynebacterium amycolatum*, *Corynebacterium auris*, *Corynebacterium glucuronolyticum*, *Corynebacterium argentoratense*, *Lactobacillus acidophilus*, *Lactobacillus crispatus*, *Lactobacillus gallinarum*, *Lactobacillus gasseri*, *Lactobacillus johnsonii*, *Lactobacillus amylovorus*, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, *Companilactobacillus farciminis*, *Lactiplantibacillus paraplantarum*, *Lactiplantibacillus pentosus*, *Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*, *Limosilactobacillus reuteri*, *Lactobacillus fermentum* subsp. *reuteri*, *Limosila ctobacillus*

mucosae, Lacticaseibacillus casei, Lacticaseibacillus paracasei, Lactobacillus delbrueckii, Lactobacillus helveticus, Lactobacillus bulgaricus, Levilactobacillus brevis, Lentilactobacillus buchneri, Limosilactobacillus fermentum, Lentilactobacillus kerifi, Lactobacillus kefir, Lactobacillus sanfranciscensis, Lentilactobacillus parabuchneri, Fructilactobacillus sanfranciscensis, Latilactobacillus curvatus, Latilactobacillus sakei, Companilactobacillus alimentarius, Ligilactobacillus salivarius, Ligilactobacillus ruminis, Ligilactobacillus animalis, Lactococcus lactis, Leuconostoc mesenteroides, Leuconostoc lactis, Leuconostoc pseudomesenteroides, Leuconostoc citreum, Leuconostoc carnosum, Pediococcus pentosaceus, Lapidilactobacillus dextrinicus, Pediococcus acidilactici, Pediococcus parvulus, Propionibacterium freudenreichii, Acidipropionibacterium acidipropionici, Cutibacterium acnes, Streptococcus salivarius subsp. thermophilus, Actinomadura roseorufa, Actinomadura yumaensis, Corynebacterium casei, Corynebacterium stationis, Enterococcus faecium, Enterococcus mundtii, Eubacterium, Bacillus amyloliquefaciens, Weizmannia coagulans, Shouchella clausii, Alkalihalobacillus clausii, Bacillus atrophaeus, Bacillus flexus, Priestia flexa, Lysinibacillus fusiformis, Bacillus licheniformis, Bacillus lentus, Lederbergia lenta, Bacillus mojavensis, Priestia megaterium, Bacillus vallismortis, Bacillus smithii, Bacillus subtilis, Bacillus pumilus, Geobacillus stearothermophilus, Bacillus paralicheniformis, Bacillus velezensis, Bacillus sonorensis, Brevibacillus brevis, Cytobacillus firmus, Bacillus toyonensis, Streptomyces albus, Kitasatospora aureofaciens, Streptomyces aureofaciens, Streptomyces azureus, Streptomyces cinnamonensis, Streptomyces lasaliensis, Streptomyces virginiae, Streptomyces lasalocidi, Actinoplanes utahensis, Clostridium butyricum, Paenibacillus lentus, Gluconobacter oxydans, Xanthomonas maltophilia, Stenotrophomonas maltophilia, Enterobacter cloacae, Enterobacter spp., Alcaligenes acidovorans, Ensifer adhaerens, Escherichia coli, Gluconobacter frateurii, Methylococcus capsulatus, Paracoccus carotinifaciens, Pseudomonas fluorescens, Rhodopseudomonas palustris, Serratia rubidaea, Sphingomonas elodea, Alcaligenes odorans, Alcaligenes faecalis, Ensifer fredii, Ketogulonicigenium vulgare.

New names are also considered during the exercise. For instance:

- *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus plantarum*
- *Companilactobacillus farciminis*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus farciminis*
- *Lactiplantibacillus paraplantarum*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus paraplantarum*
- *Lactiplantibacillus pentosus*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus pentosus*
- *Lacticaseibacillus rhamnosus*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*
- *Lactobacillus casei rhamnosus*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus rhamnosus*
- *Limosilactobacillus reuteri*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus reuteri*
- *Lactobacillus fermentum* subsp. *reuteri*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus reuteri*
- *Limosilactobacillus mucosae*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus mucosae*
- *Lacticaseibacillus casei*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus casei*
- *Lacticaseibacillus paracasei*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus paracasei*
- *Lactobacillus bulgaricus*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus delbrueckii* subsp. *bulgaricus*
- *Levilactobacillus brevis*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus brevis*
- *Lentilactobacillus buchneri*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus buchneri*
- *Limosilactobacillus fermentum*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus fermentum*
- *Lentilactobacillus kerifi*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus kerifi*
- *Lentilactobacillus parabuchneri*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus parabuchneri*
- *Fructilactobacillus sanfranciscensis*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus sanfranciscensis*
- *Latilactobacillus curvatus*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus curvatus*
- *Latilactobacillus sakei*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus sakei*

- *Companilactobacillus alimentarius*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus alimentarius*
- *Ligilactobacillus salivarius*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus salivarius*
- *Ligilactobacillus ruminis*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus ruminis*
- *Ligilactobacillus animalis*: formerly known as *Lactobacillus animalis*
- *Lapidilactobacillus dextrinicus*: formerly known as *Pediococcus dextrinicus*
- *Acidipropionibacterium acidipropionici*: formerly known as *Propionibacterium acidipropionici*
- *Cutibacterium acnes*: formerly known as *Propionibacterium acnes*
- *Streptococcus salivarius* subsp. *thermophilus*: formerly known as *Streptococcus thermophilus*
- *Weizmannia coagulans*: formerly known as *Bacillus coagulans*
- *Shouchella clausii*: formerly known as *Bacillus clausii*
- *Alkalihalobacillus clausii*: formerly known as *Bacillus clausii*
- *Priestia flexa*: formerly known as *Bacillus flexus*
- *Lysinibacillus fusiformis*: formerly known as *Bacillus fusiformis*
- *Lederbergia lenta*: formerly known as *Bacillus lentus*
- *Priestia megaterium*: formerly known as *Bacillus megaterium*
- *Geobacillus stearothermophilus*: formerly known as *Bacillus stearothermophilus*
- *Brevibacillus brevis*: formerly known as *Bacillus brevis*
- *Cytobacillus firmus*: formerly known as *Bacillus firmus*
- *Kitasatospora aureofaciens*: formerly known as *Streptomyces aureofaciens*
- *Streptomyces lasalocidi*: formerly known as *Streptomyces lasaliensis*
- *Ensifer adhaerens*: formerly known as *Sinorhizobium adhaerens*
- *Ensifer fredii*: formerly known as *Sinorhizobium fredii*

b) Fungi:

Saccharomyces cerevisiae, *Candida kefyri*, *Candida krusei*, *Candida norvegensis*, *Candida famata*, *Pichia*, *Pichia kluyveri*, *Pichia acaciae*, *Pichia pastoris*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Candida lactis-condensis*, *Candida utilis* and *Candida lusitaniae*.

Important synonyms and older names are also considered during the exercise. For instance, names corresponding to different morphs of pleomorphic fungi, like the anamorphic growth forms, are included when such a form is known:

- *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* synonym *Saccharomyces boulardii*
- *Kluyveromyces marxianus* anamorph *Candida kefyri*
- *Millerozyma acaciae* synonym *Pichia acaciae*
- *Pichia kudriavzevii* anamorph *Candida krusei*
- *Pichia norvegensis* anamorph *Candida norvegensis*
- *Debaryomyces hansenii* anamorph *Candida famata*
- *Komagataella pastoris* synonym *Pichia pastoris*
- *Komagataella phaffii* mistaken for *Komagataella pastoris*
- *Starmerella lactis-condensis* synonym *Candida lactis-condensis*
- *Cyberlindnera jadinii* anamorph *Candida utilis*
- *Clavispora lusitaniae* anamorph *Candida lusitaniae*

E.1.3. Exposure

For bacteria, exposure to the following antibiotics will be searched: *gentamicin*, *kanamycin*, *streptomycin*, *vancomycin*, *erythromycin*, *telithromycin*, *tylosin*, *ampicillin*, *fosfomycin*, *colistin*, *ciprofloxacin*, *chloramphenicol*, *thiamphenicol*, *clindamycin* and *tetracycline*.

For fungi, exposure to the following antifungals will be searched: *amphotericin B*, *nystatin*, *5-fluorocytosine*, *ketoconazole*, *fluconazole*, *itraconazole*, *voriconazole*, *posaconazole* and *isavuconazole*.

E.1.4. Comparator

Since it is expected that, in the majority of the study designs relevant for the review question, the comparator will not be available, the latter will not be included as a key element in the search strategy.

E.1.5. Outcomes of interest

The outcomes of interest to this ELS are

Question 1:

- Cut-off values for bacteria.

Question 2:

- Cut-off values for fungi.

E.1.6. Identification of the review questions

The following research questions will be addressed:

- What is the resistance/susceptibility (R/S) phenotypic profile to clinically relevant antibiotics for bacteria typically used in the food chain?
- What is the resistance/susceptibility (R/S) phenotypic profile to clinically relevant antimycotics for fungi typically used in the food chain?

E.2. Eligibility criteria for study selection

The selection of studies relevant to questions 1 and 2 will be performed applying the eligibility criteria described in [Table 1](#) below.

Table 1: Eligibility criteria for questions 1 and 2

	Criteria
Study design	No specific type of study design will be used to include/exclude relevant studies
Study characteristics	No exclusion will be based on study characteristics
Population	Taxonomic units as identified in Section 1.2
Exposure	Studies must report on at least one antimicrobial/antimycotic as listed in Section 1.3
Outcome of interest	Outcomes as listed in Section 1.5
Language	English
Time	Bacteria: from January 2013 to December 2022 (10-year time span) Fungi: from January 2003 to December 2022 (20-year time span)
Publication type	Primary research studies and secondary studies reporting previously unpublished primary studies, meta-analysis and review articles.

E.3. Literature searches

Searches will be conducted in a range of relevant information sources to identify any evidence of phenotypic analysis for antimicrobial resistance/susceptibility regarding the target microbial species.

Each search strategy will comprise two elements: the search terms ([Section 3.1](#)) and the information sources ([Section 3.2](#)) to be searched.

E.3.1. Search terms

The search strategies used to identify studies are given in Appendix F.

Each strategy will comprise two key elements:

- Microbial species as described in [Section 1.2](#) ('Target population')
- Antimicrobials and resistance as described in [Section 1.3](#) ('Exposure').

Search terms were identified in close collaboration with the information specialist; examples of such terms are the following: 'antimicrobial*', 'drug*', 'resistan*' and 'susceptib*'.

The subgroups of target microbial species will be entered on separate search lines. The search line for each group will be combined with the antimicrobials and resistance terms individually.

The searches will be limited to English but not limited by study design.

The review period will be for bacteria from January 2013 to December 2022 (10-year time span) and for fungi from January 2003 to December 2022 (20-year time span).

E.3.2. Information sources searched

The information sources (see [Table 2](#) below).

Table 2: Information sources to be searched to identify relevant studies

Information source	Interface
BIOSIS Citation Index	Web of Science platform (Clarivate)
CAB Abstracts	Web of Science platform (Clarivate)
Food Science Technology Abstracts (FSTA)	Web of Science platform (Clarivate)
MEDLINE	Web of Science platform (Clarivate)
Scopus	Scopus.com (Elsevier)
Web of Science Core Collection	Web of Science platform (Clarivate)

Search results will be downloaded from the information sources and imported into EndNote® X9 bibliographic management software. For each of the groups, within-group removal of duplicate entries will be done in EndNote® X9. Following the uploading of the species groups into the DistillerSR¹ online software, removal of duplicates will again be undertaken, using the Duplicate Detection feature.

¹ DistillerSR, Evidence Partners, Ottawa, Canada. <https://www.evidencepartners.com/products/distillersr-systematic-review-software/>

E.4. Study selection and article evaluation

To identify potentially relevant studies to be included in the review, the studies will be selected by a three-step procedure using the DistillerSR online software.

The results of the different phases of the study selection process will be reported in a flowchart (Appendix G).

E.4.1. Screening for potential relevance at the title level

Articles will initially be screened at the title level in parallel by two expert reviewers and, if needed, EFSA staff.

If the information in the title is not relevant for the research objectives (phenotypic analysis for antimicrobial resistance/susceptibility), the article will not proceed to the next step ([Section 4.2](#)).

Articles that are excluded during screening at this step will be stored in Distiller SR.

In case of doubts or divergences between the reviewers, the paper will proceed to step 2.

E.4.2. Screening for potential relevance at the title and abstract level

The articles passing the first step will undergo a screening at the abstract level in parallel by two experts.

If the information in the title and abstract is not relevant for the research objectives (phenotypic analysis for antimicrobial resistance/susceptibility), the article will not proceed to the next step ([Section 4.3](#)).

Articles that are excluded during screening at this step will be stored in Distiller SR.

In case of doubts or divergences between the reviewers, the paper will proceed to step 3.

E.4.3. Article evaluation

The aim of this step will be to confirm that the article is relevant for the exercise and, if it is, to evaluate it. It will be carried out at the full-text level.

The articles passing the second step will undergo a validation procedure carried out by two experts.

In case of disagreement, the reviewers will initially try to solve the disagreement. If this is not possible, the conflicting information will be presented for collective expert evaluation of the ELS outcome (see [Section 5](#)).

If the information contained in the article is not relevant for the research objectives, the article will not be evaluated. Articles that are not considered relevant will be stored in Distiller SR.

E.4.3.1. Questions for study selection and article evaluation

STEP 1 (Screening for potential relevance):

Question 1: Is the full text available in English and dealing with phenotypic analysis for antimicrobial resistance/susceptibility?

Option	Result
Yes	Include and continue to the article evaluation form
Full text not available	Exclude
Full text not in English	Exclude
Full text in English but not dealing with phenotypic analysis for antimicrobial resistance/susceptibility	Exclude

STEP 2 (Article evaluation):

Question 1: Is the paper dealing with resistance to at least one of the following antibiotics/antifungals?

- Antibiotics: gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin, vancomycin, erythromycin, telithromycin, tylosin, ampicillin, fosfomycin, colistin, ciprofloxacin, chloramphenicol, thiamphenicol, clindamycin and tetracycline.
- Antifungals: amphotericin B, nystatin, 5-fluorocytosine, ketoconazole, fluconazole, itraconazole, voriconazole, posaconazole and isavuconazole.

Option	Result
1. Yes	Include and continue to the next question
2. No	Exclude

Question 2: Is the paper reporting at least one of the following measures of resistance to the antibiotics?

MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration), MIC90 (minimum inhibitory concentration 90), MIC50 (minimum inhibitory concentration 50), IC90 (inhibitory concentration 90), IC50 (inhibitory concentration 50), ECOFF (epidemiologic cut-off values), ECV (epidemiologic cut-off values), MCOFF (microbiological cut-offs), MEC (minimum effective concentration), EC50 (effective concentration 50), EC90 (effective concentration 90) and Emax (maximum effect)

Option	Result
1. Yes	Include and continue to the next question
2. No	Exclude

Question 3: Is the paper reporting information related to wild-type/non-GM bacteria/yeasts?

Option	Result
1. Yes	Include and continue to the next question
2. No	Exclude

Question 4: Is the paper reporting information related to pure culture bacteria/yeasts?

Option	Result
1. Yes	Bacteria: include and continue to the next question Yeasts: include and continue to data extraction
2. No	Exclude

Question 5: Is the paper reporting information related to clinical isolate(s)? (question only for bacteria questionnaire)

Option	Result
1. Yes	Exclude
2. No	Include and continue to the next question

Question 6: Is the strain(s) defined as resistant/multi-resistant? (question only for bacteria questionnaire)

Option	Result
1. Yes	Exclude
2. No	Include and continue to data extraction

STEP 3 (Data extraction):

STEP 3.1. (identify microorganisms and antibiotics)

Question 1: Identification of the non-GM bacteria/yeast at species level.

- The article will be characterised in terms of the microorganism(s) involved.
Single-choice question: the experts will identify the microorganism(s) described in the article. If more than one microorganism is described in the paper, the form will be repeated for each microorganism.

Question 2: Strain identification (culture collection or internal code).

- Free text box

Question 3: What is the geographical origin of the microorganism?

- Countries (dropdown menu)

Question 4: Description of the isolation source of the microorganism.

- Free text box

Question 5: Which antibiotic/antimycotic is tested in the study?

- The article will be characterised in terms of the antimicrobial(s) tested.
Single-choice question: the experts will identify the antimicrobial(s) described in the article. If more than one is tested in the paper, the form will be repeated for each antibiotic and microorganism.

Antibiotics: gentamicin, kanamycin, streptomycin, vancomycin, erythromycin, telithromycin, tylosin, ampicillin, fosfomycin, colistin, ciprofloxacin, chloramphenicol, thiamphenicol, clindamycin and tetracycline.

Antifungals: amphotericin B, nystatin, 5-fluorocytosine, ketoconazole, fluconazole, itraconazole, voriconazole, posaconazole and isavuconazole.

STEP 3.2. (The questionnaire will be repeated for each species-strain-antimicrobial combination obtained in step 3.1.)

Question 1: Which type of measure for the antimicrobial activity is provided in the study?

- Not reported
- MIC (minimum inhibitory concentration)
- Others: MIC90 (minimum inhibitory concentration), MIC50 (minimum inhibitory concentration), IC90 (inhibitory concentration), IC50 (inhibitory concentration), ECOFF (epidemiologic cut-off values), ECV (epidemiologic cut-off values), MCOFF (microbiological cut-offs), MEC (minimum effective concentration), EC50 (effective concentration), EC90 (effective concentration) and Emax (maximum effect)

Question 2: Measure the value to be inserted.

- Please insert value.
- Please insert unit.

*Question 3: Is the previous value obtained following internationally recognised standards?
(indicate the methodology)*

- A dedicated free text box will appear to describe the methodology and limitation identified.

E.5. Collective expert evaluation of the ELS outcome and presentation in the EFSA Guidance

The overall results of the searches and evaluations of individual articles will be presented in tabular format for each group/subgroup and species. These results will be further evaluated collectively by EFSA experts, and the outcome will be reflected in the EFSA Guidance on the characterisation and risk assessment of microorganisms used in the food chain.

For bacteria, the final cut-off values will be established based on expert knowledge elicitation. Values established by European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing² will be used as reference when available.

For fungi, the distribution of the literature-reported MICs will be analysed by methods based on statistics involving non-linear regression curves using ECOFFinder.³

E.6. Update of the process

The literature search, study selection and collective expert evaluation will be repeated periodically.

² EUCAST Antimicrobial wild type distributions of microorganisms Database: <https://mic.eucast.org/>

³ ECOFFinder software version 2.1. <https://clsi.org/meetings/susceptibility-testing-subcommittees/ecoffinder/>